

Pest resistance—diseases

Impact of seedborne bacteria on rice seedlings

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We studied the bacterial populations in seeds of different rice cultivars and evaluated their effect on seed germination and seedling vigor.

We used serial dilution technique to examine seeds of rice cultivars Jaya, Gowrisanna, Rajamudi, Shakti, and Rajakayame for externally borne (from surface wash) and internally borne (from crushed seeds) bacterial populations. Colonies morphologically different in dilution plates were transferred separately to nutrient agar slants and Gram-stained.

The effect of bacteria on seed quality was assessed using cultures grown in nutrient broth for 24 h at 25 ± 2°C. Surface-sterilized seeds were soaked in the bacterial cultures for 24 h. Treated seeds were tested for germination using the paper towel method. Controls were seeds soaked in uninoculated medium and in sterile water. Sprouts were counted daily for 5 d. Root and shoot lengths were measured on the 5th or 14th days and a seedling vigor index calculated. Patho-

genicity of each bacterial isolate was tested by the cut-and-inoculate method.

Seeds of all five cultivars carried bacteria. Internal bacteria outnumbered external bacteria (Table 1). Most bacteria were Gram-negative and varied in size from coccus bacilli to long filamentous forms. Only one Gram-positive strain was isolated from Shakti; it was internally seedborne.

Table 1. Bacteria borne externally and internally by rice seed, Mysore, India.

Cultivar	Externally borne bacteria (10 ² cells/g of seed)	Internally borne bacteria (10 ³ cells/g of seed)
Jaya	10.0	31.0
Gowrisanna	50.0	267.0
Rajamudi	10.6	26.0
Shakti	8.5	3.0
Rajakayame	11.0	5.0

Sprouted rice seed showed differential responses to the presence of bacterial cultures. The response differed not only between bacteria, but also in terms of germination, root growth, shoot growth, and vigor. The stimulatory or inhibitory effects of bacteria toward allied hosts followed no particular pattern (Table 2). Vigor increased in Gowrisanna and decreased in Jaya, Rajamudi, and Shakti. Rajakayame seedlings showed both stimulatory and inhibitory effects.

Most of the cultures that reduced vigor were capable of producing symptoms when inoculated to rice seedlings. Symptoms included dry appearance, curly blades, and yellow leaves. Bacterial infection in general produced varied effects.

Of 18 isolates tested, only two interacted with Shakti; 15 interacted with Gowrisanna (Table 2). The vigor of Gowrisanna seedlings suggests that the bacterial colonization of its seeds may be beneficial. □

Table 2. Cross interaction of bacterial isolates. ^a Mysore, India.

Culture ^b isolated from cultivar	Cultures tested (no.)	Jaya		Gowrisanna		Rajamudi		Shakti		Rajakayame	
		IC (no.)	VI	IC (no.)	VI	IC (no.)	VI	IC (no.)	VI	IC (no.)	VI
Gs	6	3	*	4	+	3	-	1	-	2	*
Sh	5	4	-	4	+	4	-	Nil	*	-	+
Rm	3	2	-	3	+	2	-	1	-	Nil	*
Rk	2	1	-	2	+	2	-	Nil	*	Nil	*
Jaya	2	1	-	2	+	2	-	Nil	*	1	-

^a VI = Vigorindex: - = inhibition, + = stimulation, * = no effect compared to control. IC = Cultures causing interaction.

^b Gs = Gowrisanna, Sh = Shakti, Rm = Rajamudi, Rk = Rajakayame.

Identifying tolerance for rice tungro (RTV)-associated viruses in rice varieties using severity index scoring and serology

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We used the new scoring method to evaluate 15 selected varieties for resistance to or tolerance for RTV.

Each variety was seeded at 20 seeds/pot, with three replications. At 10 d after seeding, one pot/variety was batch-inoculated for 3 h in a cage containing 10 viruliferous GLH/seedling. (GLH had fed on plants infected with rice tungro bacilliform [RTBV] and rice tungro spherical [RTSV] viruses for 4 d.)

Seedlings were scored individually 4 wk after inoculation. Leaf samples were also collected and indexed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

(ELISA) for the presence of RTV-associated viruses.

Based on their severity index (score 1-3 = resistant, 4-6 = intermediate, and 7-9 = susceptible), Utri Rajapan (Acc. 16684), ARC11554, Pankhari 203, Balimau Putih, Utri Merah (Acc. 16680), and Tilockkachari can be considered resistant (see table).

Based on ELISA, only ARC11554 and Utri Merah had less than 10% infection by RTV-associated viruses. Utri Rajapan, Pankhari 203, Balimau